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Interview

INTERVIEW WITH MS. TAMARA PEMOVSKA, A RESEARCH ASSISTANT ON THE *IMPULSE* PROJECT

The written interview with Tamara Pemovska (TP) was conducted at the beginning of December 2021 by Contemporary Psychiatry and Medicine (CP&M).

CP&M: Ms. Pemovska, thank you for participating in this interview. Please summarise your CV below, in 5-6 lines:

TP: Thank you for your invitation. Since I was in high school, I was most fascinated by biology and psychology. This interest led me to study medicine

at the University of St. Cyril and Methodius in Skopje, North Macedonia. However, with the desire to receive an interdisciplinary education and more research opportunities I continued my studies at the University College Utrecht, Netherlands. There I obtained a Liberal Arts and Sciences degree with a major in Biomedical Sciences and a minor in Psychology. Thereafter, I worked on a health innovation project about management of cardiovascular diseases. In 2018, as a result of my interest in both life and social sciences, I obtained a Master of Science in Public Health from the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine in the United Kingdom. For the past three years I have been working at Queen Mary University of London, researching the implementation of a psychosocial intervention for people with psychosis in Southeast Europe as part of the IMPULSE project.

CP&M: We are informed that you are the first author on a paper with qualitative study results recently published in a prestigious journal, BMC Psychiatry (<https://rdcu.be/cCHRE>). Could you please provide some details on the methodology used in that paper?

TP: Dr. Arenliu and I share first authorship on this paper. It was a large piece of work, involving 32 focus groups with 174 participants from five Southeast European countries. The participants were a mix of mental health clinicians, policymakers, patients diagnosed with psychosis and caregivers. In an iterative process, we developed a list of questions to be discussed during the focus groups based on our research aim to explore participants' views on barriers, facilitators and perceived benefits of implementing a psychosocial intervention for treatment of psychosis in the included countries. At the beginning of each focus group, participants were familiarized with the intervention through a presentation by the focus group's facilitators. The discussions were first transcribed in their original language and then translated to English so that the international analysis team could work collaboratively. The analysis of the qualitative data was complex and laborious. It involved four researchers undertaking thematic framework analysis, first developed by Jane Ritchie and Liz Spencer in the late 1980s and now widely used in health research. This analysis method provided us with the necessary structure and flexibility. We began by reading through the transcripts' translations to familiarize ourselves with the data and develop preliminary coding lists.

Through consensus-based decision-making we combined the individual lists in one, containing categorized codes grounded in both concerns related to our research question and additional data-driven ones from the familiarization process. To ensure that all researchers involved were applying the coding lists in the same manner, we coded the same transcripts until there were no longer any discrepancies. Once all data were coded and categorized, they were summarized per focus group participant for each code category, after which we turned to identifying patterns and articulating our interpretation of the data in light of our research aim. Crucially, we were regularly consulting with all focus group facilitators during the analysis process and involved patients and carers as experts by experience in the research.

CP&M: Could you please share some advantages of qualitative studies over quantitative ones?

TP: When choosing the suitable research method, the most important thing to consider is the particular research question of interest. Qualitative research pursues ‘what’ and ‘how’ questions, in comparison to ‘how many’ or ‘how often’ that are the largely the focus of quantitative research. So, where quantitative research deals with numbers, qualitative research is concerned with text and language. Quantitative studies are used to quantify the problem and generalize findings from a larger group of participants. However, the strengths of qualitative research lie in having a question, but not a hypothesis; resisting assumptions; involving fewer participants to provide detailed description of a range of individual meanings, experiences, and perspectives; and viewing data as something that is produced and not solely collected, often discarding the principles of objective analysis. Qualitative research is oriented towards generating new concepts and theoretical insights rather than testing them and as such it is helpful in refining research questions. Overall, qualitative studies provide a greater insight or understanding of a particular topic and social phenomena of interest.

CP&M: Could you list some general limitations of qualitative studies?

TP: Concepts such as validity and reliability, which imply a positivist view of the world consisting of a stable reality that can be precisely measured, do not

apply very clearly to qualitative research that mostly has an interpretivist worldview where reality is perceived to be unstable and as such a broader concept of credibility of findings is used. The findings from a qualitative study relate only to a few specific environments and individuals, so it is impossible to show that they apply to other populations and circumstances. This limits the generalizability of the findings and conclusions. However, providing enough information of the context in which the qualitative study took place, can help the reader to determine the degree to which the findings are related and applicable to their own population under study. Qualitative research is heavily reliant on individual qualities of the researcher and their subjective interpretations, thus it is necessary that well-trained and experienced researchers are involved and that their role in the research is accounted for.

CP&M: What are the issues you have faced while preparing and carrying out qualitative studies?

TP: As part of the IMPULSE project I was involved in multi-national and multi-language qualitative research, which presented many methodological challenges as a result of working across both cultural and linguistic boundaries. The results were intended for publication in English language peer-reviewed journals that implied risk of losing fundamental features of qualitative research. There is a risk of losing contextual-specific meaning informative of what the participant aimed to express and having researcher's questions formulated in an unnatural way that are difficult to understand by the participant. Additionally, there is danger in imposing a single viewpoint on international data. Working in an international context, one has to consider the associated diversity and how best to standardize carrying out the qualitative study. Furthermore, a large amount of resources, such as time, staff, finance, are needed to execute such qualitative research, usually in a context of competing priorities.

CP&M: Could you please give some pieces of advice to young researchers who want to plan and conduct a qualitative study in the field of mental health?

TP: I would encourage researchers to attend relevant training courses and strengthen their qualitative research skills, begin the qualitative analysis from

the outset of the research study, be clear on what the analysis is for, analyse iteratively from ‘above’ (i.e. utilizing pre-existing ideas) and ‘below’ (i.e. utilizing ideas found in the data), go beyond description of the data and make interpretations, embrace the unknown as there is no simple tool set for conducting qualitative analysis, and finally, utilize available qualitative data management software to help with the large amounts of text involved.

CP&M: If you want to write something else, not covered by these interview questions, please feel free to do so here.

TP: Qualitative research is a crucial part of the development, implementation and assessment of programmes aimed at improving mental health outcomes. It is vital to ensure that contextual-specific features are not lost when carrying out such research and to work within research principles that encourage partnership and equity.

CP&M: Thank you for your responses. They might be useful and interesting for young mental health researchers, clinicians who would like to conduct the aforementioned type of studies and researchers whose work is dominated by quantitative studies but are interested in carrying out a qualitative one.

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